

Work Package 7, Milestone 7.6: The quality analysis workflow for predicted complexes

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Introduction

Macromolecular interaction is a central theme of functional genomics, subject to large-scale genetic and biochemical studies in model organisms. Most gene products, whether protein or RNA, perform their functions in cells by interacting with other gene products, forming complexes. The dysregulation or disruption of these complexes often leads to disease as they play a crucial role in all cellular processes. Characterizing protein-protein interactions and assemblies, and understanding the principles that governs them, are therefore more than ever at the center stage of today's molecular biology.

There is a good case for testing *in silico* methods that generate structural models of the assemblies by docking their components. The nature of docking experiments allows us to test our current understanding of the principles of macromolecular interactions, and also to encode our understanding in computational methods. All computational predictions hence need to be validated both in terms of model quality and also experimentally, to see how close the model is to an experimentally determined model. As docking methods improve, reliable models will greatly help in designing future experiments and to push the boundaries of currently available algorithms.

Previous early attempts critically assessed docking procedures by comparing their performance in blind trials, in which the X-ray structures of the components are known and that of the complex were made available only at the time of evaluation (Wodak and Janin, 1978; Wodak and Janin, 2002). Since 2000, a community-wide effort called CAPRI (Critical Assessment of PRedicted Interactions) has been organized to do a large-scale, blind predictions of structures of protein-protein complexes. In recent years, this has extended to protein-nucleic acid complexes, and in the latest round of CAPRI the targets were protein-sugar complexes. In 17 years, CAPRI has allowed dozens of groups in the structural biology community to predict 130 complexes, offered by crystallographers as targets prior to publication.

In CAPRI, models of these complexes are submitted by predictor groups and assessed by comparing their geometry to the X-ray structure and by evaluating the quality of the prediction of the regions of interaction and of the pairwise residue contacts. For this project, the aim is to expose the assessment method for public use, by providing a complex assessment server that users can upload their predicted complexes to and have the assessment geometry and quality results as output.

Associated parameters

Schematic illustration of the quality measures used to evaluate predicted models in CAPRI.

Source: (Mendez, et al., 2005)

A specific procedure was developed in early rounds of CAPRI to assess geometric and biological properties of the models (Lensink, et al., 2007). For convenience, the larger component of a complex is called the receptor R, and the other component, the ligand L. The R and L epitopes are the regions of the R and L surface that make the interaction, comprising all residues that have atoms less than 5 Å apart in the target X-ray structure. After least-square superposition of R in the model and target, the geometric quality of the model is judged from the **RMS distance L_{rms}** between C-alpha atoms of L in the model and target, and by the rotation angle rL and translation dL needed to further superimpose L.

However, L_{rms}, rL and dL concern the whole ligand, often a large protein in CAPRI targets, and they may not represent the quality of the fit where it matters, that is, in the contact regions. Thus, another useful parameter in assessing the geometry of the model is the **interface RMS distance I_{rms}**, calculated on C's of the epitopes only.

The biological quality of the models was judged on the prediction of, first, the R and L epitopes, then, of the pairwise contacts between R and L residues. If the R epitope comprises N_R residues in the target, n_R of which make ligand contacts in the model, the ratio $f_R = n_R/N_R$ measures how well the model predicts the R epitope; its equivalent f_L does the same for the L epitope. A good model should also say which residues of R are in contact with which residues of L. This is measured by the **fraction of native contacts f_{nc} = nc/N_c**, where N_c is the number of residue pairs in contact in the target, and nc the number of those native contacts that are present in the model. Because nc can be artificially increased by pushing the ligand into the receptor,

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all models that have too many non-native contacts are also rejected: this is more than the average number in other models plus two standard deviations.

In CAPRI assessment, the parameters **Irms**, **Lrms**, and **fnc** are combined to rank models into the categories ‘incorrect’, ‘acceptable’, ‘medium’ and ‘high-quality’. In models of the “high-quality” and “good” categories, a majority of epitope residues and at least 30% of the contact pairs are correctly predicted ($fnc > 0.3$), and the L epitope is very close to its position in the X-ray structure ($Irms < 2 \text{ \AA}$). Such models reproduce the overall geometry and many biologically significant features of the interaction, but not necessarily its atomic details. Models with 10%–30% of the native contact pairs and $Irms$ between 2 \AA and 4 \AA , are placed in the “acceptable” category. Although their geometry is poor, they should still be useful for site-directed mutagenesis and other experiments, because a large part of the epitopes must be correctly identified to yield $fnc > 0.1$.

At the end of a CAPRI round, all the docking models are assigned to one of the four categories by the official CAPRI assessor. Using these parameters in the query system, generally good and bad predictions can be grouped for each round, or based on individual target, or even for each individual group.

CAPRI criteria for assessing the quality of docking models.

Source: (Lensink and Wodak, 2013)

Quality analysis workflow

Figure 1: Phase I of the quality analysis workflow

The quality analysis workflow is divided into two phases; phase 1 is described in Figure 1 whereas phase II is described in Figure 2. Phase I involves steps that are taken prior to the evaluation of the user's complex input. In a nutshell, a user would provide the 3D coordinate files of the unbound components and the predicted complex to the server. The server would then read the target structure, separate it into its ligand and receptor constituents, calculate the interaction surface of the receptor and ligand epitopes, and check that the target fulfils a set of arguments defined in the program.

Phase II of the workflow includes the implementation of the bulk of the methods implemented by the quality analysis program. After assessment parameters have been set, sequence alignment between the model and the target is performed. Interface residues of the ligand and receptor are then identified, for which an error would be triggered if the numbers were not identical. Matching chains for the receptor and ligand are then identified. Following this, the common residues and structurally invariant residues are identified from the interface residues and the target sequence. Users' prediction is then projected onto the interface of the receptor as defined in the target. The contact and clash list between the ligand and receptor are then generated. Several values are then calculated, including the Irms, solvent area difference and Lrms. To calculate the ligand and receptor molecular rmsd, the receptor is first fit to the target so that the relative orientations are within acceptable values, and then the ligand theta angle is calculated after re-rotation. The interface side-chain rmsd is also calculated, and interface waters are analysed. Finally, based on the parameters calculated, the prediction quality is categorized as either a 'high', 'medium', 'acceptable', 'incorrect', or 'unclassified' prediction.

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Figure 2: Phase II of the quality analysis workflow

Data model

At present, there is no defined data model for the workflow. The data representation will be developed in collaboration with the CAPRI community.

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